

HEALTH/SICKNESS

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Abstract: The article talks about the importance of a healthy lifestyle, people's responsibility for their health, and diseases caused by bad habits. The article also provides an overview of global health rankings and the importance of healthy eating. It is noted that poor nutrition and inactivity cause problems such as serious diseases, especially heart disease, diabetes and depression.

Key words: health, disease, healthy lifestyle, poor diet, heart disease, diabetes, nutrition, physical activity, sleep, disease prevention, fast food, healthy diet, heart attacks, Canadian scientists, obesity.

We know that each person's lifestyle and life expectancy depends on him and his actions. This is because some people do not take their health seriously and get many diseases as a result. For example, as a result of lack of sleep, they get *heart disease, kidney disease, high blood pressure, diabetes, depression, stroke* and other diseases. Even when they are injured, they don't pay attention, saying "it's a *minor injury*, not serious", and they take different medicines *OVER the counter*.

It is true that these drugs help the wound to heal, but they do affect other organs in the body enough. And as a result, a minor injury disappears and they start *suffering* from a *serious injury*. In addition, many people now live a sedentary lifestyle, that is, they do not take their health seriously, do not eat a balanced diet, do not exercise regularly, do not get enough sleep on time, mainly they don't go to their monthly *medical examinations* and as a result *many people get sick and drop like flies*.

In 2017, In the famous American newspaper "Time" magazine, in the article entitled "Healthy, prosperous lifestyle around the world", you can find a number of news and changes about health. This article highlights the following in the welfare-2017 ranking has been announced. This rating is conducted annually by the British think tank The Legatum Institute. And this rating took into account aspects such as "safety and security", "education", "health care" and "personal freedom".

“Norway, New Zealand and Finland are leading the welfare-2017 rating. Yemen is in the last place.

Kazakhstan was ranked 72nd, Kyrgyzstan – 82nd, and Tajikistan – 102nd among Central Asian countries. But, unfortunately, Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan are not in the rating,” says one of the participants of the meeting. Of course, there are enough reasons to say so. Because for some people in our country, wealth is important, not health. Most of the people work hard day and night to acquire money, property, and wealth, but they don’t care about their healthy lifestyle.

I think that a healthy diet plays a significant role in a healthy lifestyle. And in such a case, we have a question. What is the relationship between healthy eating and healthy life?

Famous nutritionists answer this question as follows. Eating healthy provides the necessary nutrients that your body needs to create new cells, clear out toxins and simply function every day! Eating healthy now can help prevent future diseases such as diabetes and cancer. You will have more energy and be more alert.

Canadian scientists have a different opinion on this question. That is, eating a lot of fruits and vegetables are beneficial our life and this is one of the most important diet habits. Vegetables and fruit are packed with nutrients (antioxidants, vitamins, minerals and fiber) and help you maintain a healthy weight by keeping you full longer. Fill half your plate with vegetables and fruit at every meal and snack.” As we mentioned above, many diseases and problems arise as a result of not eating properly. The saddest thing is that not only old people but also children eat fast food and food rich in harmful chemicals due to improper nutrition. In addition, they do not eat properly and regularly. As a result, such children suffer from obesity.

Conclusion

Based on the information provided in the article, it is clearly stated that the health of a person largely depends on his lifestyle, diet and physical activity. It is shown that each person is responsible for his own health, and that poor nutrition and lack of physical activity are the main causes of heart disease, diabetes and other diseases. The article also discusses the role of healthy eating and global health research. It is emphasized that a healthy lifestyle is important not only in the field of health, but also in the general well-being of a person. People are losing their health due to improper diet, avoiding necessary medical examinations, lack of physical activity. At the same time, the article discusses the promotion of a healthy lifestyle and its benefits at the national and international levels. The article calls for encouraging the young generation to eat healthy and to eliminate bad habits.

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